

L(d, 2, 1)-LABELING OF N-SUN GRAPH

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ABSTRACT

Let G be a graph with vertex set $V(G)$. An $L(d, 2, 1)$ - labeling of a graph G is a function f from the vertex set $V(G)$ to the set of positive integers such that for any two vertices x, y , if $d(x, y) = 1$, then $|f(x) - f(y)| \geq d$; if $d(x, y) = 2$, then $|f(x) - f(y)| \geq 2$; and if $d(x, y) = 3$, then $|f(x) - f(y)| \geq 1$. The $L(d, 2, 1)$ - labeling number $k(G)$ of G is the smallest positive integer k such that G has an $L(d, 2, 1)$ - labeling with k as the maximum label. In this paper we determine the $L(d, 2, 1)$ - labeling of n -sun graphs.

Keywords: $L(d, 2, 1)$, n -sun

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INTRODUCTION:

In [2] Jean Clipperton generalized of $L(3, 2, 1)$ -labeling of complete graphs, complete bipartite graphs, path and cycles into $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling where $d \geq 4$. In this chapter we study the $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of the n -sun graph. Where we refer of [2], we illustrate the results with figures.

Definition 1.1

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a graph and f be a mapping $f: V \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$. f is an $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of G if, for all $x, y \in V$,

$$|f(x) - f(y)| \geq \begin{cases} d & \text{if } d(x, y) = 1 \\ 2 & \text{if } d(x, y) = 2 \\ 1 & \text{if } d(x, y) = 3 \end{cases}$$

Definition 1.2

The $L(d, 2, 1)$ -number, $k_d(G)$, of a graph G is the smallest natural number k such that G has an $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling with k as the maximum label. An $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of a graph G is called a minimal $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of G if, under the labeling, the highest label of any vertex is $k_d(G)$.

Note.

If 1 is not used as a vertex label in an $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of a graph, then every vertex label can be decreased by one to obtain another $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of the graph. Therefore in a minimal $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling 1 will necessarily appear as a vertex label.

Definition 1.3

A n -sun graph U_n as a graph on $2n$ nodes consisting of a central complete graph K_n with an outer ring of n vertices, each of which is joined to both endpoints of the closet outer edge of the central core.

Theorem 1.4

$k_d(U_n) = 4n - 5 + d$ for all $n \geq 5$ where U_n is the sun graph with $2n$ vertices.

Proof:

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a sun graph U_n with $V = \{u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_{2n}\}$ is the vertex set and $E = \{u_i u_{i+1} / 1 \leq i \leq 2n - 1\} \cup \{u_i u_j / 1 \leq i, j \leq 2n; i \neq j\} \cup \{u_{2n} u_1\}$ is the edge set of G . We first show that $k_d(U_n) \geq 4n - 5 + d$. Let f be a minimal $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of the sun graph U_n . We have the distance between any two of the

odd vertices $u_1, u_3, \dots, u_{2n-1}$ is one and hence their corresponding labeling should differ by d .

Also we have the distance between any two of the even vertices u_2, u_6, u_{10}, \dots is three and hence their corresponding labeling should differ by one.

Similarly, we have the distance between any two of the even vertices u_4, u_8, u_{12}, \dots is three and hence their corresponding labeling also should differ by one. Since f is minimal, $f(u_1)$ has to be label as 1. As there are $2n$ vertices with $|f(u_i) - f(u_j)| \geq 1$ for $1 \leq i, j \leq 2n$ with $i \neq j$, the minimal $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of the sun graph can not be less than $[2n + 2n - 5 + d]$. That is, $(4n - 5 + d)$. We prove that the minimal $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of sun graph U_n is exactly $(4n - 5 + d)$ by giving a suitable labeling. We define the minimal $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling for the vertices of the sun graph U_n as follows.

Case (i)

Let us first consider the case when n is odd. Let $n = (2m + 1)$.

Define

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & i=1 \\ \frac{n+i-3}{2} + d & i=2 \\ \frac{i-4}{4} + d & i=0 \pmod{4} \\ \frac{2n+i-4}{4} + d & i=2 \pmod{4} \\ \frac{2n+3i-7}{2} + d & i=1 \pmod{2} \end{cases}$$

Here, the labels assigned to the vertices are $u_1, u_4, u_8, u_{12}, \dots, u_{2n-2}, u_2, u_6, u_{10}, \dots, u_{2n}$ are respectively $1, d, d+1, d+2, \dots, (d+n-1)$ and the vertices $u_3, u_5, u_7, \dots, u_{2n-1}$ are respectively $(d+n+1), (d+n+4), (d+n+7), \dots, (d+4n-5)$. Therefore, in this case, the $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling is $(d+4n-5)$.

Case (ii)

Now let us consider the case when n is even. Let $n = 2m$. Define

$$f(u_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & i=1 \\ n-1+d & i=2 \\ \frac{i-4}{4} + d & i=0 \pmod{4} \\ \frac{2n+i-6}{4} + d & i=2 \pmod{4} \\ \frac{2n+3i-13}{2} + d & i=1 \pmod{2}, i \neq 3 \\ 4n-5+d & i=3 \end{cases}$$

Here, the labels assigned to the vertices are $u_1, u_4, u_8, u_{12}, \dots, u_{2n}, u_6, u_{10}, \dots, u_{2n-2}, u_2$ are respectively $1, d, d+1, d+2, \dots, (d+n-2), (d+n-1)$ and the vertices $u_5, u_7, \dots, u_{2n-1}, u_3$ are respectively $(d+n+1), (d+n+4), (d+n+7), \dots, (d+4n-5)$. Therefore, in this case, the $L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling is $(d+4n - 5)$.

Thus the above labeling pattern shows that $k_d(U_n) = d + 4n - 5, n \geq 5$.

Example 1.5

$L(d, 2, 1)$ -labeling of sun graphs U_{16} and U_{15} are given in Figure 1.5.1 and 1.5.2 respectively.

U_{16} (Fig.1.5.1) $k_3(U_{16}) = 62$

U_{15} (Fig.1.5.2) $k_3(U_{15}) = 58$

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